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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSUBRAMANI bearing USN6SU17AO001 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsMEGHANA MADHAVAN bearing USN6SU17AO002 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJALY PRIYADARSHINI BOSE bearing USN6SU17AO003 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FARHA SIDDIQUE T H bearing USN6SU17A0004 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEX C ANDREWS bearing USN6SU17A0005 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSHILPA SAJEEV bearing USN6SU17AO006 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSAHLATH NAFIYA V bearing USN6SU17AO007 has completed his/her Internship at Baby memorial Hospital Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA U K bearing USN6SU18AO001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUJA M S bearing USN6SU18AO002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BINILA K B bearing USN6SU18AO003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA bearing USN6SU18AO004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVIKA P S bearing USN6SU18AO005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DILSHA SHERIN N S bearing USN6SU18AO006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAYIS MUHAMMED P bearing USN6SU18AO007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NISHANA S A P bearing USN6SU18AO008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RISHIKESH P V bearing USN6SU18AO009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHANA SHERIN V P bearing USN6SU18AO010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEKUTTY V bearing USN6SU18AO011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms T M FATHIMA SHADA bearing USN6SU18AO012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUPRIYA K P bearing USN6SU18AO013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VRINDA V V bearing USN6SU18AO014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZIYADHA SIDDIQUE bearing USN6SU18AO015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUTHA PALAN THONSE bearing USN6SU18AO016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOVINDRAJ bearing USN6SU18AO017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOOLYA DIVYAJYOTHI VITTALA bearing USN6SU18AO018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka, mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAYAK KARTHIK bearing USN6SU18AO019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PREETHI bearing USN6SU18AO020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANJANA D NAYAK bearing USN6SU18AO021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWATHI S bearing USN6SU18AO022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas hospital Mukka,mangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation Theatre technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHILA K Sbearing USN 6SU19AO001 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEENA CATHERIN bearing USN 6SU19AO002 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA UNNIKRISHNAN bearing USN 6SU19AO003 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHA PURUSHOTHAMAN bearing USN 6SU19AO004 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHLY SHAJI bearing USN 6SU19AO005 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN DEV N Sbearing USN 6SU19AO006has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DRISHYA S DAMODARAN bearing USN 6SU19AO007 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA S BASHEER bearing USN 6SU19AO008 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARITHA MURALI bearing USN 6SU19AO009 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JAISON M SIMON bearing USN 6SU19AO010 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JEFFIN JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU19AO011 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOJO JOSE bearing USN 6SU19AO012 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOYICE JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU19A0013 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K.SNEHA bearing USN 6SU19A0014 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KEVIN SIMON bearing USN 6SU19AO015 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEENU S DEV bearing USN 6SU19A0016 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED NASIH P Tbearing USN 6SU19AO017has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL HASEEB bearing USN 6SU20AO001 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADRIKA K bearing USN 6SU20AO002 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AGNAS TREESA JINNY bearing USN 6SU20AO003 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAY DEV T bearing USN 6SU20AO004 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJAL P bearing USN 6SU20AO005 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJU JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU20AO006 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE C S bearing USN 6SU20AO007 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN KUMAR N P bearing USN 6SU20AO008 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GLADYS ANN REJI bearing USN 6SU20AO010 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JACOB JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20AO011 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINSY WILSON bearing USN 6SU20AO012 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHIN J LAL bearing USN 6SU20AO013 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSHY JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20AO014 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHITHA MANIKANDAN bearing USN 6SU20AO015 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYAMATH MURSHIDA M A bearing USN 6SU20AO016 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED FASIR T P M bearing USN 6SU20AO017 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SHIHAS K.S. bearing USN 6SU20AO018 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAKHIL PRASAD P P bearing USN 6SU20AO019 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAVYA P bearing USN 6SU20AO020 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKITA GANGADHAR NAIK bearing USN 6SU20AO021 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NUF AIS RAHMAN K.K. bearing USN 6SU20AO022 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms P A ARYA bearing USN 6SU20AO023 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RITHIYA P T bearing USN 6SU20AO024 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINSON SABU bearing USN 6SU20AO025 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINYA bearing USN 6SU21AO001 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISHWARYA P K bearing USN 6SU21AO002 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA S VIJAYAN bearing USN 6SU21AO003 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSILAMOL S bearing USN 6SU21AO004 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA APPUKUTTAN bearing USN 6SU21AO005 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DIV DAS bearing USN 6SU21AO007 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SHANA bearing USN 6SU21AO008 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAWAZ bearing USN 6SU21AO009 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA S bearing USN 6SU21A0010 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOUTHAMI E T bearing USN 6SU21AO011 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOVINDAM RAGHAVENDRA bearing USN 6SU21AO012 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARIS P NAZEER bearing USN 6SU21AO013 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ISHAN K bearing USN 6SU21AO014 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JYOTHIKA M bearing USN 6SU21AO015 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K P BASIM ANSAF bearing USN 6SU21AO016 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED RAMIL U K bearing USN 6SU21AO017 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUJEEB RAHMAN K B bearing USN 6SU21AO018 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAHLA R S bearing USN 6SU21A0019 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHA ABDUL SALIM bearing USN 6SU21AO020 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAGARLAL A bearing USN 6SU21AO021 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAHANA NOUSHAD K bearing USN 6SU21AO022 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHALBIYA ABBAS bearing USN 6SU21AO023 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRINIDHI S bearing USN 6SU21AO024 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SONA M K bearing USN 6SU21AO025 has completed his/her internship at APOLLO hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAKHILDEV N bearing USN 6SU19CC001has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAMRUTHA K MANOJ bearing USN 6SU19CC002has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUROOP K DAS bearing USN 6SU19CC003has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FABINA. P V bearing USN 6SU19CC004 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SANA AHAMMAD bearing USN 6SU19CC005 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsJUMANATH V bearing USN 6SU19CC006 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSANCHITHA B bearing USN 6SU19CC007 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAFINA ANAS bearing USN 6SU20CC001 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAKHITHA A B bearing USN 6SU20CC002has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsALBIN TOM ANI bearing USN 6SU20CC003has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMITHA RAJ bearing USN 6SU20CC004 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSHA S bearing USN 6SU20CC005 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVIKA K P bearing USN 6SU20CC006 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDHANYA DEVASSY bearing USN 6SU20CC007 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LAKSHMI PRASAD bearing USN 6SU20CC008 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMADHURA bearing USN 6SU20CC009 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMALHARUDHEEN K P bearing USN 6SU20CC010has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED AFLAH K bearing USN 6SU20CC011 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVANI E S bearing USN 6SU20CC012 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAJEESHA BINO bearing USN 6SU20CC013 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsR PALLAVI bearing USN 6SU20CC014 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsRAZI RAZAK P C bearing USN 6SU20CC015 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA S bearing USN 6SU20CC016 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMMA MOHAMED bearing USN 6SU20CC017 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMMA O S bearing USN 6SU20CC018 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHANAMOL bearing USN 6SU20CC019 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHELHA V bearing USN 6SU20CC020 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSHOBLE K MATHEW bearing USN 6SU20CC021 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSTHUTI DINESH bearing USN 6SU20CC022has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SYED ABDUL KHALIQ bearing USN 6SU20CC023 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VEENA VIJAYANATHAN bearing USN 6SU20CC024 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUPRIYA BIJUMON bearing USN 6SU20CC025 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANSIF AK bearing USN 6SU21CC002 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsFAJID MOHAMMED bearing USN 6SU21CC003 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOURIKRISHNA. S bearing USN 6SU21CC006 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsINDRAJITH M bearing USN 6SU21CC007has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED BASITH C H bearing USN 6SU21CC008 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED BILLAL BIN JAMAL bearing USN 6SU21CC009 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAYANTHARA RAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC010 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSALMATHUL MISIRIA K A bearing USN 6SU21CC011 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSANGEETH M SHAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC012has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHERVEN SAJI bearing USN 6SU21CC013 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEEMA ISHA bearing USN 6SU20CP001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUT CHINTAN bearing USN 6SU20CP002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BENGIA NUNU bearing USN 6SU20CP003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA M P bearing USN 6SU20CP004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIDHIN P bearing USN 6SU20CP005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIDDHI SREENIVASAN bearing USN 6SU20CP007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms STEPHIN GEORGY ABRAHAM bearing USN 6SU20CP009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYAN A NAIR bearing USN 6SU21CP001 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHAYA K bearing USN 6SU21CP002 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN N bearing USN 6SU21CP007 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEREENA ELIZABETH SHAJI bearing USN 6SU21CP008 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms N AKANKSHA M ACHAR bearing USN 6SU21CP009 has completed his/her internship St. ANTHONY'S CHARITY institute Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FASMIN YOUSUF bearing USN 6SU20CP802 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOYCE ANJANA RODRIGUES bearing USN 6SU20CP803 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARY DEVASIA C bearing USN 6SU20CP805 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAKSHITHA bearing USN 6SU20CP806 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RESHMA BASHEER MOOCHIKKAL bearing USN 6SU20CP807 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAHANA D bearing USN 6SU20CP808 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUNBULA T bearing USN 6SU20CP810 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAAISHA NIHALA T bearing USN6SU21CP801 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL T SIMON bearing USN6SU17CV001 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio vascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARNOLD CHRIS ALEX bearing USN6SU17CV002 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio vascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DAYANA DSOUZA bearing USN6SU17CV003 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio vascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BINDSHAD A Pbearing USN6SU17CV004 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PETER TINIL N Jbearing USN6SU17CV005 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio vascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AYSHA ASMA bearing USN6SU17CV006 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms P K AYSHA SHANIAbearing USN6SU17CV007 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio vascular technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALBIN MICHAEL bearing USN 6SU18CV001 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALTHAF THAHA bearing USN 6SU18CV002 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJALI MIRIAM ALLELUIA bearing USN 6SU18CV003 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANMITHA S SHETTY bearing USN 6SU18CV011 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHA A J bearing USN 6SU18CV012 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD BADUSHA B bearing USN 6SU18CV013 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED SHAMIL bearing USN 6SU18CV014 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIRANJAN P KUMAR bearing USN 6SU18CV015 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHIT BABU bearing USN 6SU18CV016 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFA ABDUSSAMAD PARAMBAN bearing USN 6SU18CV017 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANA FATHIMA N K bearing USN 6SU18CV018 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDESH bearing USN 6SU18CV019 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SENSTIN P J bearing USN 6SU18CV020 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SURAJ bearing USN 6SU18CV021 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SURAMYA S bearing USN 6SU18CV022 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA K bearing USN 6SU18CV023 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms USTAD ZEESHAN SAHEB bearing USN 6SU18CV024 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZEB A bearing USN 6SU18CV025 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore, in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABIN ANZAR bearing USN 6SU19CV001 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ACHUTH A bearing USN 6SU19CV002 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL PRAKASH M P bearing USN 6SU19CV003 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL RAGHAV bearing USN 6SU19CV004 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALAN SUNNY bearing USN 6SU19CV005 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSEEF MOTTAMMAL bearing USN 6SU19CV006 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE VV bearing USN 6SU19CV007 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DAYA SATHYAN bearing USN 6SU19CV008 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOUTHAM CHANDRA A bearing USN 6SU19CV009 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIBA FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU19CV010 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESLIN M M bearing USN 6SU19CV012 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN JAISON bearing USN 6SU19CV013 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LOYAL SHELLY bearing USN 6SU19CV014 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MIZHAB V C bearing USN 6SU19CV016 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHAFID C S bearing USN 6SU19CV017 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIMMEY GEORGE bearing USN 6SU19CV019 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NISHITH bearing USN 6SU19CV020 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RABEEH V V bearing USN 6SU19CV021 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAISA NAVAS bearing USN 6SU19CV022 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAVEENA R bearing USN 6SU19CV023 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROOPA NAIK bearing USN 6SU19CV024 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms S SREEREJ bearing USN 6SU19CV025 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMNAD M bearing USN 6SU19CV026 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHEIKH ZAHID AHMED bearing USN 6SU19CV027 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHUBHASHREE SHAILAJA SALIAN bearing USN 6SU19CV028 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREELAKSHMI SASIDHARAN bearing USN 6SU19CV029 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA PAVITHRAN bearing USN 6SU19CV030 has completed his/her internship at metro Hospital Calicut in the first Semester of the Cardiovascular technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAYA Tbearing USN6SU20CV001 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKASH Rbearing USN6SU20CV002 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJANA MARIA ALLELUIA bearing USN6SU20CV004 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA K Sbearing USN6SU20CV005 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARMAINbearing USN6SU20CV006 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYA UDAYAN bearing USN6SU20CV007 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BASILICA MARIYANA D Sbearing USN6SU20CV008 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHAVYASREE Mbearing USN6SU20CV009 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVI NANDANA B bearing USN6SU20CV010 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANISHA PERVIN K Pbearing USN6SU20CV011 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHILSHA Mbearing USN6SU20CV012 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA FAHMIDA C Hbearing USN6SU20CV013 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms H MANASA RAVINDRA bearing USN6SU20CV014 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HALEEMA ASHIQ bearing USN6SU20CV015 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRITHIK MURALI bearing USN6SU20CV016 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms IBRAHIM ASHIQ bearing USN6SU20CV017 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JULIA SHAJI bearing USN6SU20CV019 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUBASIR ZAMIL Mbearing USN6SU20CV021 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHARIKA E Gbearing USN6SU20CV022 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUFSA NA C K bearing USN6SU20CV024 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINCY K JOSE bearing USN6SU20CV028 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINCY KOSHY bearing USN6SU20CV029 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUPRIYA J Vbearing USN6SU20CV030 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIMANYU A bearing USN6SU21CV001 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABIN A bearing USN6SU21CV002 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADWAITH C bearing USN6SU21CV003 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL V KUMAR bearing USN6SU21CV004 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEENA THOMAS bearing USN6SU21CV005 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHAD AHAMMED bearing USN6SU21CV006 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIKA ULLAS C K bearing USN6SU21CV007 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASIF NOUSHAD bearing USN6SU21CV008 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AVANTHIKA VINILKUMAR bearing USN6SU21CV009 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AZIL BIN ASHRAF K bearing USN6SU21CV010 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BINSHA BASHEER PANIKAVEETTIL bearing USN6SU21CV011 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAMDA NOWSHAD bearing USN6SU21CV012 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HANS FERDINAND D SOUZA bearing USN6SU21CV013 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHIN SUDHAKAR bearing USN6SU21CV014 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSHNA SHAJI bearing USN6SU21CV015 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYAM RUMAIZA bearing USN6SU21CV016 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MASOODH M bearing USN6SU21CV017 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED FAIZ H bearing USN6SU21CV018 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SADHUL bearing USN6SU21CV019 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA BABU bearing USN6SU21CV020 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NUSAIR SIDDIQUE bearing USN6SU21CV021 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAJNA S SHETTIGAR bearing USN6SU21CV022 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHITH P K bearing USN6SU21CV023 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFA ALI bearing USN6SU21CV024 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFUWA PERWIN bearing USN6SU21CV025 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHABEEBA PUTHANVEETIL bearing USN6SU21CV026 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIVARANJINI B bearing USN6SU21CV027 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYA M M bearing USN6SU21CV028 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHANTH V AMEEN bearing USN6SU21CV029 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VYSHAKH U bearing USN6SU21CV030 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABEL KURUVILLA JACOB bearing USN6SU20DF001 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAY V V bearing USN6SU20DF002 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINAV VINOD bearing USN6SU20DF003 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK SAM PRAVEEN bearing USN6SU20DF004 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ENJOY P J bearing USN6SU20DF005 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GADHASHREE B bearing USN6SU20DF006 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GODWIN VARUGHESE K bearing USN6SU20DF007 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARIKRISHNAN K bearing USN6SU20DF008 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN KUMAR K bearing USN6SU20DF009 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIYO BIJU bearing USN6SU20DF010 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MELWIN POLY bearing USN6SU20DF011 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MUHAD bearing USN6SU20DF012 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL JOSEPH K J bearing USN6SU20DF013 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFUVAN A K bearing USN6SU20DF014 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SELSA ANNA VARGHESE bearing USN6SU20DF015 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIDHARTH SHYAM bearing USN6SU20DF016 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEHARI S bearing USN6SU20DF017 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ACHU SHIBU bearing USN 6SU21DF001 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND SHANKAR bearing USN 6SU21DF003 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYAN JAYANTH bearing USN 6SU21DF005 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHUL PRAKASH D bearing USN 6SU21DF006 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVADEVAN B bearing USN 6SU21DF007 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOKUL K V bearing USN 6SU21DF008 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA V V bearing USN 6SU21DF009 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GURUNATHAPPAGOUDA KARALAKUNTI bearing USN 6SU21DF010 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JIBRAN T JALEEL bearing USN 6SU21DF011 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANAV SUNIL bearing USN 6SU21DF013 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHANA P bearing USN 6SU21DF014 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL MAHADEV bearing USN 6SU21DF015 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIVED AV bearing USN 6SU21DF016 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERIN SUSAN KURIAN bearing USN 6SU21DF020 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms UTHARA A M bearing USN 6SU21DF022 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FOSEAYA ANJU BEJOY bearing USN 6SU21DF023 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MIDHUN SUNILKUMAR bearing USN 6SU21DF024 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PULAGALA ACHSAH NIRMAL JYOTHI bearing USN 6SU20CS801 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms EAGALA DURGA NANDINI bearing USN 6SU20CS802 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VENKETESH Rbearing USN 6SU20CS803 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA P bearing USN 6SU21CS801 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FEMIN GEORGE bearing USN 6SU21CS802 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms UDAYSHANKAR K P bearing USN 6SU21CS803 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHA GIREESH bearing USN 6SU21CS804 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINAV SALGUNAN bearing USN 6SU18FS001 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIRAM A K bearing USN 6SU18FS002 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHARA T bearing USN 6SU18FS003 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAY M bearing USN 6SU18FS004 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA ANOOP bearing USN 6SU18FS005 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BILAL MURTHAZA ABOOBACKER bearing USN 6SU18FS006 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms C S VAISHAKH bearing USN 6SU18FS007 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA JAYACHANDRAN bearing USN 6SU18FS008 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANUSHA T bearing USN 6SU18FS009 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIMA MARIYAM SHEEN bearing USN 6SU18FS010 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOHNS JOY bearing USN 6SU18FS011 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KEERTHI R bearing USN 6SU18FS012 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KHADEEJA AFRIN SHAREEF bearing USN 6SU18FS013 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LINEX KRISHNA bearing USN 6SU18FS014 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHIMA BINEESH bearing USN 6SU18FS015 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD FAYAZ A K bearing USN 6SU18FS016 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL G bearing USN 6SU18FS017 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRITHESH LAWRENCE FERNANDES bearing USN 6SU18FS018 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RODRIGUES JOYCEL LEOCADIA bearing USN 6SU18FS019 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA . P bearing USN 6SU18FS020 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRUTHI BOSE S bearing USN 6SU18FS021 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSMITHA.K.S bearing USN 6SU18FS022 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms THAMBURU E. bearing USN 6SU18FS023 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIPIN BABU C bearing USN 6SU18FS024 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUDAS NISHAD bearing USN 6SU18FS025 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIRAMI M R bearing USN 6SU19FS001 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABYMOL BINOY bearing USN 6SU19FS002 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYA P bearing USN 6SU19FS003 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITI NAGARAJ bearing USN 6SU19FS004 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAYA bearing USN 6SU19FS005 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHA bearing USN 6SU19FS006 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARUN ROY bearing USN 6SU19FS007 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVIKA M bearing USN 6SU19FS008 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GANGA SURESH bearing USN 6SU19FS009 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOURI PARVATHI S bearing USN 6SU19FS010 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K SHYAAM MOHAN bearing USN 6SU19FS011 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIJIN L bearing USN 6SU19FS012 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ASLAM NASAR bearing USN 6SU19FS013 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PEEYUSH S bearing USN 6SU19FS014 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAMSHIYA T T bearing USN 6SU19FS015 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RITHUVARNA C bearing USN 6SU19FS016 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SCHUMACHER bearing USN 6SU19FS017 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRAVYA S RAI bearing USN 6SU19FS018 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIRKAZI MOHD FURQUAN MOHD FARHATH bearing USN 6SU19FS019 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SONA K bearing USN 6SU19FS020 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEHARI C K bearing USN 6SU19FS021 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEJA S bearing USN 6SU19FS022 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSHIN SAMUEL GEORGE bearing USN 6SU19FS023 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TALUKH YANGFO bearing USN 6SU19FS024 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms THEERTHA M bearing USN 6SU19FS025 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AADITH SUGEESH bearing USN 6SU20FS001 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEN BENNY bearing USN 6SU20FS003 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWATHY PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU20FS006 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BIMAL S G bearing USN 6SU20FS007 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DELMA DSOUZA bearing USN 6SU20FS009 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVIKA P S bearing USN 6SU20FS010 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOKUL RAJ K K bearing USN 6SU20FS011 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA P bearing USN 6SU20FS012 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESLIN GEORGE T N bearing USN 6SU20FS013 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIKA M GOPI bearing USN 6SU20FS014 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LAVANYA T bearing USN 6SU20FS015 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHANA G BHAT bearing USN 6SU20FS016 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED THANVEER M P bearing USN 6SU20FS017 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAJMA P A bearing USN 6SU20FS018 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIRANJANA P P bearing USN 6SU20FS019 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PUNYA JAYACHANDRAN bearing USN 6SU20FS020 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAJ KRISHNAN R bearing USN 6SU20FS021 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANLEAO MATHEW bearing USN 6SU20FS022 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SOORYA K bearing USN 6SU20FS023 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAIBHAV SANTHOSH bearing USN 6SU20FS024 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU R bearing USN 6SU20FS025 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYA NARAYANAN bearing USN6SU21FS001 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISHWARYA bearing USN6SU21FS002 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA S S bearing USN6SU21FS003 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALINA GEORGE bearing USN6SU21FS004 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANKITHA BRUNETTE DSOUZA bearing USN6SU21FS005 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHITHA bearing USN6SU21FS006 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BAVITHA J bearing USN6SU21FS007 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHETHAN SKANDA S J bearing USN6SU21FS008 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANALAKSHMI D bearing USN6SU21FS009 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAIZ AHMED bearing USN6SU21FS010 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUNAINA KUNNUKATTIL NASEER bearing USN6SU21FS011 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LANKESH K B bearing USN6SU21FS012 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MALAVIKA ANAND bearing USN6SU21FS013 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MITASHREE M M bearing USN6SU21FS014 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAIK MEGHANA RAGUNATH bearing USN6SU21FS015 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDAN RAVI bearing USN6SU21FS016 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRACHI PONNAMMA M K bearing USN6SU21FS017 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAVEEN CHANDRAN bearing USN6SU21FS018 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAGEE RAJAN bearing USN6SU21FS019 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAHUL UDAY KUMAR SHETTY bearing USN6SU21FS020 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SINDHUSAGAR R bearing USN6SU21FS021 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA A bearing USN6SU21FS022 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAMSHI S KOTIAN bearing USN6SU21FS023 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIJAY JAISON bearing USN6SU21FS024 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms YASHWIN S SALIYAN bearing USN6SU21FS025 has completed his/her internship at Regional FSL Mangalore in the first Semester of BSC the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIKA ASHOKAN bearing USN 6SU20FS803 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NITHIN S bearing USN 6SU20FS804 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RESHMA SURESH bearing USN6SU21FS801 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA FERNANDES SELESTIN bearing USN6SU21FS802 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHNAVI R.J bearing USN6SU21FS803 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSAGILA bearing USN6SU21FS804 has completed his/her internship at in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA T bearing USN 6SU20FC801 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUJITH C V bearing USN 6SU20FC802 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANWAYAKRISHNA P bearing USN 6SU20FC803 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIKA S NAIR bearing USN 6SU20FC804 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHIRA K K bearing USN 6SU20FC805 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIK O K bearing USN 6SU20FC806 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms REEBA JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20FC808 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA JACOB P J bearing USN 6SU20FC809 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms STEENA M T bearing USN 6SU20FC810 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJANA PRASAD bearing USN 6SU21FC801 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANN SONA AUGUSTINE bearing USN 6SU21FC802 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYA R J bearing USN 6SU21FC803 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHELSEA B ABY bearing USN 6SU21FC805 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHESHKUMAR RAGHAVENDRA S bearing USN 6SU21FC806 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MALAVIKA SUNIL KUMAR bearing USN 6SU21FC807 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SURYA K U bearing USN 6SU21FC808 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA M B bearing USN 6SU21FC809 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NOUFI N bearing USN 6SU21FC810 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUTHA M A bearing USN 6SU17MI001 has completed his/her internship at AJ Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIDHA FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU17MI002 has completed his/her internship at AJ Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PARAGATI SRIKANTH bearing USN 6SU17MI003 has completed his/her internship at AJ Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHAMMED NAZIM ABDULLA bearing USN 6SU18MI001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMAL M A bearing USN 6SU18MI002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN R NAIR bearing USN 6SU18MI003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BERLEY KOSHY bearing USN 6SU18MI004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DONET THANKACHAN bearing USN 6SU18MI005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRIDHIN K bearing USN 6SU18MI006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms IFA RUDA bearing USN 6SU18MI007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SUHAIL bearing USN 6SU18MI010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAJUMUNNISA NAJEEB P U bearing USN 6SU18MI012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19

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CERTIFICATE

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWANI SATHEESAN N P bearing USN 6SU20MI007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHAVYA KRISHNA P bearing USN 6SU21MI010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms C H MUFSINA MUHAMMED RAFI bearing USN 6SU21MI011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SANA bearing USN 6SU21MI012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAYIZ SAKEER HUSSAIN bearing USN 6SU21MI013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINTO JOHNY bearing USN 6SU21MI014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KHADEEJA ZOYA T K bearing USN 6SU21MI015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUFEEEDA E bearing USN 6SU21MI016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ANAS C K bearing USN 6SU21MI017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHAL NASHID bearing USN 6SU21MI018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHITHA MANOHAR K bearing USN 6SU21MI019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIFANA K M bearing USN 6SU21MI020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHIHABUDEEN K S bearing USN 6SU21MI022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSMAYA M bearing USN 6SU21MI023 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms V K ANAMIKA bearing USN 6SU21MI024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZUHA HUSSAIN bearing USN 6SU21MI025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARSHA T V bearing USN 6SU17ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADARSH P P bearing USN 6SU17ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAYA bearing USN 6SU17ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREETHU BABU A bearing USN 6SU17ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHILPA K V bearing USN 6SU17ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KISHAN S KULAL bearing USN 6SU17ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREENIMA MUKUNDAN bearing USN 6SU17ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL RAHMAN JASEEL bearing USN 6SU17ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RIBIANGLIN LYNGDOH bearing USN 6SU17ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2017-2018

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADEENA A bearing USN6SU18ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGH DEV K bearing USN6SU18ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NEETHU V bearing USN6SU18ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PALLAVI bearing USN6SU18ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SADA FAROOQUI bearing USN6SU18ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms TENZIN LHATON KEE bearing USN6SU18ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDULLA bearing USN6SU19ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALFIYA Ubearing USN6SU19ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDHU KRISHNA K Mbearing USN6SU19ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSWAR AHAMMED K Pbearing USN6SU19ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANURAG Sbearing USN6SU19ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHREE A Vbearing USN6SU19ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA REHAN bearing USN6SU19ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GEETHU Pbearing USN6SU19ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JIJISHA Pbearing USN6SU19ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAVYASHREE A C bearing USN6SU19ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KRITHI Kbearing USN6SU19ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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**This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYOLA DOLLY FERRAObearing
USN6SU19ML012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical
science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEHA SAJI bearing USN6SU19ML013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ASHIK K Sbearing USN6SU19ML014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIMRAH NOORJHAN bearing USN6SU19ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANCHITHA SHETTY bearing USN6SU19ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE A bearing USN 6SU20ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DILNA E bearing USN 6SU20ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DIYA P S bearing USN 6SU20ML012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FAYIS ABDUL LATHEEF bearing USN 6SU20ML013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FEBIN SUNNY bearing USN 6SU20ML014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNAN T J** bearing USN **6SU20ML015** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAYA ROOSH MEHAR M bearing USN 6SU20ML016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JEBIN BAJI bearing USN 6SU20ML017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SAHLE PEEDIKAYIL bearing USN 6SU20ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA DIVAKAR bearing USN 6SU20ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHANA P bearing USN 6SU20ML020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAYUJYA A P bearing USN 6SU20ML021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHEIK MUHAMMED RIYAF bearing USN 6SU20ML022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIVAKUMAR B L** bearing USN **6SU20ML023** has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWETHA GANGAN C bearing USN 6SU20ML024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZIFA KHAN bearing USN 6SU20ML025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL HULAIF M bearing USN 6SU21ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA M V bearing USN 6SU21ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE RAJENDRAN K bearing USN 6SU21ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AYISHATHUL SHAHLA bearing USN 6SU21ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DAYANA bearing USN 6SU21ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DENWIN DSOUZA bearing USN 6SU21ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FARAHATH SAFEEDA S H bearing USN 6SU21ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA MUFEEDA bearing USN 6SU21ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAWTHAMKRISHNAN A U bearing USN 6SU21ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HIBA RAHMAN P K bearing USN 6SU21ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESNA JASEEL M bearing USN 6SU21ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED MUZAMIL bearing USN 6SU21ML015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NABISHAD MISRIYA K bearing USN 6SU21ML016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHITHA NARAYANAN bearing USN 6SU21ML017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms P MOHAMMED AKHEEL bearing USN 6SU21ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms POURNAMI K bearing USN 6SU21ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUMANA bearing USN 6SU21ML020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHYAMA K bearing USN 6SU21ML021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHNAVI NARAYANAN bearing USN 6SU21ML022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA RAVEENDRAN bearing USN 6SU21ML023 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAITNA K bearing USN 6SU21ML024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms YASHODHA RAMESHA GOWDA bearing USN 6SU21ML025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL RAHIMAN BISHARATH bearing USN 6SU18OP001 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALKKA MARIYA bearing USN 6SU18OP002 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsKAVYA bearing USN 6SU18OP003 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MARSHAD N bearing USN 6SU18OP004 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2018-2019

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK S Gbearing USN6SU19OP001 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUTHA M KURUP bearing USN6SU19OP002 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms POORNIMA Mbearing USN6SU19OP003 has completed his/her internship at Puthalath eye hospital, Calicut in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRIDHYA KRISHNAN Tbearing USN6SU20OP001 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KRISHNAJA Kbearing USN6SU20OP002 has completed his/her internship at Vasam eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MONISHA bearing USN6SU20OP003 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAKSHITH P Nbearing USN6SU20OP005 has completed his/her internship at Vasana eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZULFA KHATON bearing USN6SU20OP008 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Anjitha P V. bearing USN 6SU21OP001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/ Anjua D. bearing USN 6SU21OP002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsARCHA D BINU bearing USN 6SU21OP004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BENITA ABEY bearing USN 6SU21OP005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsBHAVANA K V bearing USN 6SU21OP006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARSHINA KUNHAMMED V bearing USN 6SU21OP007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JASMY M SEBASTIAN bearing USN 6SU21OP009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSUHANA THASNIM P V bearing USN 6SU21OP012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THEERTHA V bearing USN 6SU21OP013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TUSHITH YASHWANTH SHETTY bearing USN 6SU21OP014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VARSHA K bearing USN 6SU21OP015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIDA FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU21OP016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIVEDITHA GIRISHAN KUNDAN bearing USN 6SU17PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMAL C S bearing USN6SU18PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DONA BIJUMON DANIEL bearing USN6SU18PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA SAJANAN bearing USN6SU18PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABUBAKAR bearing USN 6SU19PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsATHULYA K bearing USN 6SU19PT004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsCHRISTO CHACKO ABRAHAM bearing USN 6SU19PT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGEORGE SAJU bearing USN 6SU19PT006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMIDHUN MATHEWS bearing USN 6SU19PT007has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHABEER bearing USN 6SU19PT008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHMMED AJAS B bearing USN 6SU19PT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMUSAB bearing USN 6SU19PT010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNANDANA BABU N bearing USN 6SU19PT011has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsPOOJA VISWAS bearing USN 6SU19PT013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsPUNNYA MADHU C bearing USN 6SU19PT014has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PUNYA PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU19PT015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSADIYA SIDHEEK bearing USN 6SU19PT016has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSREE M V bearing USN 6SU20PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsASWATHY R bearing USN 6SU20PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGODSON P B bearing USN 6SU20PT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPINAATH K bearing USN 6SU20PT006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMALAVIKA S bearing USN 6SU20PT007has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNANDINI P bearing USN 6SU20PT008has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERIN MARYAM LAL bearing USN 6SU20PT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAVYASHREE bearing USN6SU21PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHITH S NAIR bearing USN6SU21PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUSHIKA CHYRMANG bearing USN6SU21PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHA ALFA bearing USN6SU17RD001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSURYA GAYATHRI bearing USN6SU17RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSREE S bearing USN6SU17RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANASWARA B T K bearing USN6SU17RD004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MILAN JOSE bearing USN6SU17RD005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VARSHA BALAN K bearing USN6SU17RD006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsDIXION V ANDREWS bearing USN6SU17RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsSUJEESH S bearing USN6SU17RD008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIJA PADMANABHAN bearing USN6SU18RD001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKASH Abearing USN6SU18RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA SASIDHARAN bearing USN6SU18RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHAITHRA P Kbearing USN6SU18RD006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHRISYA G NAIR bearing USN6SU18RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESNA SEBASTIAN bearing USN6SU18RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIMSHAD ALI A Cbearing USN6SU18RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAVEENA V Vbearing USN6SU18RD012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAVITHA N PARAMANATTI bearing USN6SU18RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAISHWARYA RAJ C V bearing USN6SU19RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANAND M P bearing USN6SU19RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDERONAJITH T K bearing USN6SU19RD008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVIKA PAVITHRAN bearing USN6SU19RD009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPIKA G S bearing USN6SU19RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JISNA M M bearing USN6SU19RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHU JIJU bearing USN6SU19RD012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMANYA P bearing USN6SU19RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsR KRISHNA PRABHU bearing USN6SU19RD014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsRAJISHA N P bearing USN6SU19RD015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINAND K bearing USN 6SU20RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMAN MUHAMMED V S bearing USN 6SU20RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAPARNA BENNY bearing USN 6SU20RD004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAPARNNA CHANDRAN J P bearing USN 6SU20RD005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsASHISHA SURESH bearing USN 6SU20RD006has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsBISMI SAHAROF B bearing USN 6SU20RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVIKA SURESH bearing USN 6SU20RD008has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GANGA P V bearing USN 6SU20RD009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JERIN VARGHESE bearing USN 6SU20RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAREENA SIBY bearing USN 6SU20RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ADHIL C S bearing USN 6SU20RD012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHAHEEM E M bearing USN 6SU20RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED THAFAD T bearing USN 6SU20RD014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED WASIM P bearing USN 6SU20RD015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNASIYA N bearing USN 6SU20RD016has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRUTHVI bearing USN 6SU20RD018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAKHIMOL K R bearing USN 6SU20RD019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSARIKA bearing USN 6SU20RD020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHEJIN V SHIBU bearing USN 6SU20RD021has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSONA SHAJI bearing USN 6SU20RD022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSREEPRABHA P.J. bearing USN 6SU20RD023 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VASIL AHAMMED B M bearing USN 6SU20RD024 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIDHURAJ bearing USN 6SU20RD025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADHITHYA Sbearing USN 6SU21RD001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDA LAKSHMI T Sbearing USN 6SU21RD004has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDHU K Sbearing USN 6SU21RD005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms APARNA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AROMAL SHIBU bearing USN 6SU21RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN BABU P V bearing USN 6SU21RD008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AYISHA THASHREEFA U C bearing USN 6SU21RD009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVAMRUTHA T V bearing USN 6SU21RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU21RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA FIDHA K K** bearing USN **6SU21RD012** has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIZA AAMI bearing USN 6SU21RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GRESHMA Rbearing USN 6SU21RD014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAIFA IBRAHIM bearing USN 6SU21RD015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRIDYA K V bearing USN 6SU21RD016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUBEENA bearing USN 6SU21RD017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PARVATHY ANI bearing USN 6SU21RD019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANTHEEZ MOHAMMED M Tbearing USN 6SU21RD020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA V P bearing USN 6SU21RD021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAMIKA V Mbearing USN 6SU21RD022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NOWFIYA Nbearing USN 6SU21RD023has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAMSIYA MOL Sbearing USN 6SU21RD024has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMEENA Sbearing USN 6SU21RD025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARIPRIYA H NAIR bearing USN6SU17RC001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms S ARATI bearing USN6SU17RC002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARJUN MANIKUTTAN PILLAI bearing USN6SU17RC003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2017-18.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND K BAIJU bearing USN 6SU18RC001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FERAL RASHEED bearing USN 6SU18RC002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JEFFIN PHILIP bearing USN 6SU18RC003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LALISH Rbearing USN 6SU18RC004has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHA ANNA VARGHESE bearing USN 6SU18RC005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHAHEER bearing USN 6SU18RC006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMIL ASHRAF bearing USN 6SU18RC007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERLAT ANGIE JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU18RC008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWATHI R AJAY bearing USN 6SU18RC009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU bearing USN 6SU18RC010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2018-19.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsABINLAL H bearing USN6SU19RC001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsASHWATHI KUMAR K bearing USN6SU19RC002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUSTIN THOMAS bearing USN6SU20RT012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIYANA UBAIDULLA bearing USN6SU20RT013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED HAMZATH ADIL Kbearing USN6SU20RT016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ABDUL SALAM T Kbearing USN6SU20RT018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAJU MOIDEEN bearing USN6SU20RT021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHUMAIL HAMAD C P V bearing USN6SU20RT022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEGANGA C V bearing USN6SU20RT023 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms STELLA MARY bearing USN6SU20RT024 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms UNNIMAYA P Jbearing USN6SU20RT025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHILNA MACHA P T bearing USN 6SU21RT019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHRAVYA bearing USN 6SU21RT020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU ASHOK bearing USN 6SU21RT025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Respiratory therapy programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHMED SHAHZADH bearing USN 6SU20IV001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDIVYA DINESHAN bearing USN 6SU20IV002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms V AMRUTHA BABU bearing USN 6SU21IV008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Virology and immunology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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